

HISTORY AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK FOLK INSTRUMENTS

Yusupov Farrukh Islom ugli

State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

Chief specialist of the credit module department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11254651>

Abstract: It can be observed that the musical instruments created during the development of mankind appeared one after the other from a logical point of view. According to experts, first of all, percussion instruments were born, then wind instruments, which produce sound by means of air, and then string instruments. The article provides information about the history and stages of development of Uzbek folk instruments.

Key words: national musical instrument, sound line, range, performance options, performance styles, sound timbre, sound application.

Introduction.

There are ancient and rich traditions of Uzbek folk instrument performance. After gaining independence, the development of education on folk instruments in music and art schools in our country has grown significantly. The role of Uzbek national instruments is great in the process of general cultural and aesthetic education, as well as in the promotion of musical literacy. Today, significant work is being done in the process of finding a solution to the problems in the educational system of Uzbek national instruments, improving Uzbek folk instruments. Scientific research on the development of the field is being conducted, and new generation textbooks are being created.

The contributions of folk craftsmen and musicians to the improvement of musical instruments are incomparable. Government decisions on the introduction of folk instruments into the education system have been developed in connection with the teaching of folk instruments according to the notation system. Education on the notation system has been introduced in educational institutions, and national musical instrument workshops are operating. In 1938, under the initiative of Ashot Ivanovich Petrosyans, the Uzbek folk instruments orchestra was founded under the Uzbek State Philharmonic, in this extensive and complex process, the orchestra of national instruments was formed by A.I. Petrosyans, under the Tashkent State Conservatory *"People's Orchestra The opening of the department and faculty, the establishment of demand and production of national musical instruments, the activities of polyphonic national musical ensembles, the emergence of specially written works for various musical instruments. It was the first step in the development of music art. Uzbek folk*

musical ensembles and groups began to form. The activity of national musical ensembles was a new phenomenon in the history of Uzbek musical culture" in turn, a number of artistic tasks were set before the Ensembles. The composition of the Uzbek National Instrumental Ensemble and its musical groups were formed. The main distinguishing features of the groups were preserved.

A group of wind instruments.

Flute piccolo is a newly created instrument with unique range and range, performance possibilities and styles. He was able to occupy an important position in the folk instrument ensemble and orchestra.

The flute is a widely used instrument in Uzbekistan, and with its range and range, performance possibilities and the uniqueness of its styles, it has a role in folk orchestras and ensembles.

Trumpet, trumpet - It is distinguished by its structure, performance possibilities, styles, sound timbre, sound range and range, application.

Koshnay - The structure of the instrument, the material of which it is made, the uniqueness of its sound, performance styles and possibilities, sound range and range are different. A group of stringed instruments performed with percussion and nohunsher. (Dusts and Law);

Due to the uniqueness of the family of changs and the law, their types, tuning and timbre, performance styles, range, they are among the folk instrument orchestras and ensembles. Prima rubobi, Alt rubobi, Metsosoprano rubobi can be included in the group of words performed by mizrobli, click, nokhun and bow. These instruments are newly created, with their register, structure and tuning, sound range and range, they have taken the place of the People's Instrument Orchestra.

The Kashkar rubobi and the Afghan rubobi are considered to be a reworked type of musical instrument, and due to their structure and tuning, sound range and timbre, performance possibilities and styles, and the uniqueness of the appliqué, they are included in the folk instrument orchestras and ensembles. In ancient times, oud was considered a widespread musical instrument in the territory of Uzbekistan, and processing was also carried out in a small way. Structure and tuning vary according to sound range and timbre, performance styles and capabilities. Prima dutori and Alt dutori are considered newly created instruments, and due to their structure and tuning, sound range, performance styles, and the breadth of their possibilities, they have taken a place in the People's Instrument Orchestra. Reworked tenor dutor, secunda dutor, dutor bass, dutor contrabass are newly created instruments, and based on their

structure, sound range and tuning, performance styles and possibilities, they have an incomparable place in folk instrument orchestras and ensembles. Xalq dutori has long been considered a widespread instrument in the territory of Uzbekistan, and it is not only the favorite music of the people, but its place in folk instrument orchestras and ensembles is unique. Tanbur, Sato sozi are also one of the ancient musical instruments and have been reworked. Structure and adjustment. Sound range. With its performance methods and capabilities, it has taken a place in the folk orchestra and ensembles.

Percussion instruments used in the Uzbek folk orchestra, their types. One of the percussion instruments taken from the symphony orchestra and used in the folk orchestra is Doyra, which is a widespread Uzbek folk percussion instrument. Due to the uniqueness of its structure, timbre, performance methods and possibilities, it has a small place in folk orchestras and ensembles. Instruments such as Safoil, Qayroq, Buben, Uchburchak, Tarelka, Litavra are among the folk instrument orchestras and ensembles due to their antiquity, performance styles and capabilities. Their role in various musical groups is incomparable. Such instruments have been processed and improved, and with their structure and tuning, sound range, performance styles and capabilities, they have taken a worthy place in the folk instrument orchestra and ensembles. Uzbek folk instruments have improved and developed along the path of historical development, and today they are lovingly performed not only in our republic, but also in the ensembles of sister nations. In the stage of development, new words are created based on existing words, and musical words are being enriched.

References:

1. Akbarov Il. "Music dictionary" Tashkent "San'at" publishing house, 1997.
2. Askarov A. "History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan" Tashkent., "Fan" 1992.
3. Vyzgo T.S. "Muzikalnye instrumenty Sredney Azii" (Istoricheskie ocherki) - Moscow., 1980.
4. Irgashev G'. "Afghan Rubobi" textbook, Tashkent, "San'at" publishing house, 2004
5. Matyokubov O. Farobi "About the basics of Eastern music" Tashkent., 1986.

